

LINGUACULTURAL PROBLEM OF THE LITERARY TRANSLATION FROM UZBEK INTO ENGLISH (ON THE MATERIALS OF "BYGONE DAYS" BY ABDULLAH QODIRI)

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Annotation: Translating literature from one language to another is a complex and intricate process. It requires not only linguistic accuracy but also cultural sensitivity and an understanding of the social and historical context. When translating from Uzbek to English, especially with a classic work like "Bygone Days" by Abdullah Qodiri, several linguacultural issues arise. This article explores these challenges and offers insights into how they can be addressed.

Key words: Culturology, translation, linguacultural issues, Bygone days, Abdullah Qodiri, novel.

Аннотация: Перевод литературы с одного языка на другой – сложный и запутанный процесс. Это требует не только лингвистической точности, но и культурной чувствительности и понимания социального и исторического контекста. При переводе с узбекского на английский язык, особенно такого классического произведения, как «Минувшие дни» Абдуллы Кодире, возникает ряд лингвокультурных проблем. В данной статье рассматриваются эти проблемы и предлагается понимание того, как их можно решить.

Ключевые слова: Культурология, перевод, проблемы лингвокультуры, Прошлые дни, Абдулла Кадири, роман.

Annotatsiya : Adabiyotlarni bir tildan boshqa tilga tarjima qilish murakkab jarayondir. Bu nafaqat lingvistik aniqlikni, balki madaniy sezgirlikni va ijtimoiy va tarixiy kontekstni tushunishni ham talab qiladi. Ayniqsa, Abdulla Qodiriyning "O'tgan kunlar" kabi klassik asarini o'zbek tilidan ingliz tiliga tarjima qilganda til madaniyatiga oid bir qancha muammolar yuzaga keladi. Ushbu maqola shu kabi qiyinchiliklarni o'rganadi va ularni qanday hal qilish mumkinligi haqida tushuncha beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Madaniyatshunoslik, tarjima, til madaniyati masalalari, O'tgan kunlar, Abdulla Qodiriy, roman.

INTRODUCTION: Dialect and culture are two things that cannot be isolated since culture influences dialect and dialect influences culture. This makes the dialect in one region diverse from another. The distinction within the social background of each dialect may be a interesting marvel that happens in

society and may be a distinction that must be regarded, not to be disputed. Moreover, it affects many things, counting the scholarly works in each portion of the locale. Writing may be a work that's immortal and continuously has its group of onlookers. Frequently, it is the item of the contemplations, encounters, and creative impulses of its creators. In expansion, the socio-cultural foundation moreover influences the scholarly work. Numerous scholarly works were born from different parts of the world, and a few are prevalent within the locale and have gotten to be globally prevalent scholarly works. This gives rise to the parties' endeavors so that the scholarly work can be examined by individuals exterior who may talk a distinctive dialect from the initial dialect of the scholarly work. After being interpreted into outside dialects, scholarly works composed in different districts of the world reach a unused gathering of people . The interpretation is an endeavor to interpret words from the source dialect to the target dialect. Abdullah Qodiri's "Bygone Days" is a seminal work in Uzbek literature, written in the early 20th century. It provides a vivid portrayal of life in Uzbekistan during the late 19th and early 20th centuries, encapsulating cultural norms, societal changes, and the complexities of Uzbek society during that era. Given its cultural significance, translating "Bygone Days" into English is a critical task, but it comes with unique challenges.

DISCUSSION

Translating literature involves more than just converting words from one language to another. It requires capturing the essence, tone, and cultural context of the original work. Here are some of the key linguacultural challenges when translating from Uzbek to English:

1. Cultural Specificity:

Uzbek culture has unique elements that may not have direct equivalents in English. Traditional customs, social hierarchies, and cultural references in "Bygone Days" can be difficult to translate without losing their meaning. Translators must find ways to convey these elements while keeping the English text accessible and understandable.

2. Idiomatic Expressions:

Uzbek, like many languages, has idiomatic expressions that don't always have direct translations in English. Translators need to determine whether to keep these expressions in their original form, provide an English equivalent, or offer explanatory notes.

3. Historical Context:

"Bygone Days" is set in a specific historical context, reflecting the societal changes in Uzbekistan during a transformative period. Translators must understand this context to ensure that the translated text retains its historical accuracy and depth.

4. Literary Style and Tone:

Abdullah Qodiri's writing style is distinctive, with a combination of narrative and descriptive elements. Translators need to capture this style in English without losing the author's unique voice and tone.

5. Names and Titles:

Proper names, titles, and honorifics in Uzbek can present challenges in translation. Translators must decide whether to keep the original names or adapt them to English conventions, considering the impact on the reader's understanding.

Translators can use several strategies to address these linguacultural challenges: This approach involves adapting cultural references to make them understandable to English-speaking readers. It requires a balance between maintaining the original's authenticity and ensuring clarity. Providing explanatory notes or footnotes can help readers understand cultural or historical references. This strategy maintains the original text's integrity while offering additional context. Working with experts in Uzbek culture and history can help translators accurately represent cultural nuances and avoid misinterpretations. In some cases, it may be best to retain the original Uzbek terms, especially when there are no direct English equivalents. This approach can add authenticity to the translation and spark curiosity among readers. By concentrating on the emotional and thematic essence of the text, translators can bridge cultural gaps and convey the story's universal appeal. Roman Abdulla Kadiri, Bygone days reveals a wide run of far reaching human points and issues. Consequently, it is especially troublesome to characterize it unambiguously. In any case, it can be fought that, having laid the foundation of the work as a brilliant cherish story, the maker was able to touch upon the complex issue of the experience between God and the monster, light and cloudiness inside the destinies of mankind. Bygone days is the essential sensible novel in Uzbek composing, and at the same time the first predominant and most considered. Analysts, as typical, especially popular the picture of national traditions in it (Makhmudova Z, 1994), emphasized its region to the individuals epos and encounter books of past centuries (Mirvaliyev S, 1962), analyzed the irrefutable roots of the events depicted in it (Aliyev A, 1967), explored the

imagination of the heroes of the unused and old time inside the work (Kuronov D, 2006). In any case, no less basic, but still not examined incorporate of the novel, without a question, is the subject of the confinement of light and murkiness, shown to us by the maker through the visual-color imagery of the made substance. Talking to the vanished world of the past, the maker as on the off chance that invites the peruser to pay thought to the impressions of the divine brilliance revealed inside the bygone time, and on the way of person alter of a individual, on the way to light, given to the peruser inside the setting of a certain colorful course of action.

CONCLUSION

Translating "Bygone Days" from Uzbek to English requires careful consideration of linguistic and cultural differences. By understanding the unique challenges and using appropriate strategies, translators can create a version that respects the original work while making it accessible to an English-speaking audience. This process not only enriches the literary landscape but also fosters cross-cultural understanding and appreciation. In this manner, the errand of an master interpreter requires bounty of in advance inquire about of author's social foundation, social rank and attitude so as to begin the extend of interpretation. There are different shapes of interpretation said inside the article by the implies of phraseological units of Abdulla Kadyri's two most freely acknowledged works. These phraseological units are accepted to claim a major significance appearing the Uzbek culture as its most excellent and colorful

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